

Secure and Power-Efficient Multi-User Scheduling in Semi-Grant-Free NOMA Networks: A Coalition Game Approach

Sofia Barkatsa¹[0009-0004-5182-439X], Panagiotis
Charatsaris¹[0000-0002-4883-8203], Maria Diamanti¹[0000-0001-7275-706X], and
Symeon Papavassiliou¹[0000-0002-9459-318X]

Institute of Communication and Computer Systems (ICCS), School of Electrical and
Computer Engineering, National Technical University of Athens, 15780 Zografou,
Greece

{sbarkatsa,pancharatsaris,mdiamanti}@netmode.ntua.gr,papavass@mail.ntua.gr

Abstract. Semi-Grant-Free (SGF) access for Non-Orthogonal Multiple Access (NOMA) has recently emerged as a hybrid scheme that integrates contention-free access for Grant-Based (GB) users with contention-based access for Grant-Free (GF) users. In this context, we consider multiple GB users scheduled via a conventional grant-request procedure to dedicated Resource Blocks (RBs), which are then opportunistically, though transparently, shared by GF users to enhance network capacity while reducing control signaling overhead and service latency. Subsequently, the challenging problem of grant-free multi-RB multi-user scheduling and admission control under strict physical layer security constraints and Quality-of-Service (QoS) requirements is addressed, aiming to maximize the number of admitted GF users and minimize their transmission power. To this end, two scheduling algorithms are designed and proposed. First, a one-shot, low-complexity greedy algorithm prioritizes GF user access to RBs and respective Signal-to-Noise-Ratio (SNR) levels based on their backoff times to the base station. Secondly, an iterative coalition game-based algorithm refines RB and SNR level scheduling decisions, with GF users acting independently as players that aim to further minimize their power consumption. The proposed scheduling framework achieves a superior tradeoff between the number of admitted GF users and power consumption, while satisfying all users' service and secrecy requirements, outperforming conventional scheduling strategies from the literature.

Keywords: NOMA · semi-grant-free scheme · multiple resource blocks · multiple users · scheduling · secrecy · power efficiency · coalition games.

1 Introduction

Non-Orthogonal Multiple Access (NOMA) has been an active research area for several years, aiming to enable multi-user multiplexing over shared resources [1]. This is achieved by leveraging the superposition property of the wireless channel

and employing advanced interference cancellation techniques at the receiver. Especially in power-domain NOMA, users transmit over the same time-frequency resources and are distinguished based on their received signal strength. So far, the majority of research has concentrated on optimizing transmission strategies -including but not limited to power control, subchannel allocation, and interference mitigation- under the assumption of perfect network state information obtained via Grant-Based (GB) user scheduling protocols. While this represents a critical step toward efficient spectral resource utilization for massive connectivity, signaling overhead and coordination complexity remain major bottlenecks.

Grant-Free (GF) access schemes have recently emerged as a necessity to overcome the limitations of conventional request-grant signaling for massive connectivity short-packet communications [2, 3]. Nevertheless, the lack of explicit coordination increases the likelihood of packet collisions, compromising system reliability. To strike a balance between signaling complexity and performance, hybrid contention-based and contention-free access schemes are studied. Semi-Grant-Free (SGF) NOMA is a hybrid access scheme inspired by the cognitive radio paradigm, where GF users transparently access and share the dedicated resources allocated to GB users within a Resource Block (RB) [4]. In this context, scheduling GF users within a given RB while ensuring strict Quality of Service (QoS) guarantees for GB users is a challenging problem that becomes even more intricate when extended to the management of multiple RBs.

In this paper, we introduce a multi-RB multi-user scheduling framework for SGF NOMA networks. GB users are assigned to different RBs, which additionally facilitate multiple GF users in a power-efficient manner, jointly considering both user QoS satisfaction and physical layer security to safeguard the system against eavesdropping. Specifically, two algorithms are designed and proposed: (a) a one-shot greedy algorithm based on a priority-based backoff assignment of GF users to RBs and Signal-to-Noise-Ratio (SNR) levels within each RB, and (b) an iterative coalition game-based algorithm, in which GF users, acting independently as players, determine the most efficient RB and SNR level assignment.

1.1 Background on SGF NOMA

Conventional GB access for NOMA transmissions relies on prior handshaking with the Base Station (BS) to acquire Channel State Information (CSI) and allocate resources (e.g., RBs, transmission power, data rates) to satisfy users' QoS requirements. The GB access procedure begins with the user transmitting a random preamble to the BS, which responds with a Random Access (RA) message containing timing alignment and resource information. This is followed by a connection request from the user and a connection resolution phase at the BS, during which any contention is resolved and dedicated resources are allocated. Once the connection is successfully established, the user proceeds with data transmission over the allocated resources.

GF transmission reduces the five-step access procedure to two phases, namely the preamble and data transmission, significantly lowering latency and enabling

support for massive connectivity. To leverage the benefits of both GB and GF access, SGF NOMA emerges as a hybrid access scheme that combines scheduled access for GB users with transparent and opportunistic access for GF users. Following the grant acquisition process, the BS is assumed to have complete CSI for all GB users and can optimally allocate transmission powers and RBs. In contrast, no prior information is available regarding the number or channel conditions of the GF users attempting access. For this reason, the BS broadcasts the current network state, including RB availability and GB user requirements, enabling GF users to make informed, autonomous access decisions [3]. Additionally, GF users transmit short preambles prior to data transmission to assist with uplink synchronization and facilitate reliable detection and decoding at the BS. To manage the complexity and improve the efficiency of these mechanisms, recent works have developed scheduling algorithms, as discussed in the following.

1.2 Related Work & Motivation

Initial efforts in user scheduling in SGF NOMA networks primarily focus on single-RB systems, laying the background for more complex multi-RB scenarios. Specifically, in [5,6] several single-RB and single-GF-user scheduling solutions are introduced and evaluated in SGF NOMA networks, such as the Maximal User Scheduling (MUS) and the Optimal User Scheduling (OUS). Both works analyze these scheduling strategies with respect to secrecy outage probability, considering active and passive eavesdropping attacks. This focus is particularly critical, as the lack of coordination between GF users and the BS inherently increases interference and thus, the risk of security breaches. The work in [6] further investigates multi-GF-user scheduling strategies in terms of secrecy performance, while the authors in [4] propose a multi-user scheduling algorithm that integrates power-matching and distributed contention mechanisms to enhance the achievable sum-rate and minimize the average age of information. To the best of the authors' knowledge, the only work addressing multi-RB multi-user scheduling in SGF NOMA networks so far can be found in [7], where the scheduling problem is modeled as a stochastic Markov game. A Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) algorithm is then proposed, enabling each user to autonomously and jointly optimize the RB and transmission power level selection within each RB.

In the broader context of user scheduling and resource management for next-generation wireless networks, distributed and low-complexity game-theoretic solutions have gained significant attention. Especially matching games have been successfully applied to solve the device-edge server association problems in edge computing systems, for instance, in [8]. A matching game provides an initial feasible association between devices and servers, while a coalition formation game is subsequently employed to refine the initial solution by accounting for the externalities, i.e., the influence of one device's decisions on others. In this way, improved system-wide utility is achieved. Similarly, the work in [9] defines a many-to-many matching game to jointly optimize sub-channel assignment and power allocation in a downlink NOMA network, achieving system-wide sum-rate and user fairness. Compared to RL or DRL algorithms, matching and coalition

games offer lower computational complexity, and improved scalability, while requiring no training phase, making them more practical and suitable for ad-hoc and grant-free scheduling in dynamic network environments.

1.3 Contributions & Outline

In this paper, we aim to address the gap in the literature on multi-RB multi-user scheduling in SGF NOMA networks by proposing a low-complexity, distributed framework that operates without the need for pretraining, making it well-suited for ad-hoc and grant-free dynamic environments. The framework includes two scheduling algorithms, namely a greedy-based and a coalition game-based algorithm, which can be employed independently or in combination to enhance performance. Both algorithms' objective is to simultaneously accommodate multiple GB users over dedicated RBs and multiple GF users that transparently and opportunistically share GB users' resources, while ensuring that all users' data rate and secrecy requirements are met with the minimum power consumption. The main contributions of this paper are summarized as follows.

1. The system model of a multi-RB multi-user SGF NOMA network in the presence of an eavesdropper is introduced, and the joint assignment of RBs and discrete SNR levels is jointly addressed to ensure both service and secrecy constraints are satisfied in the most power-efficient manner.
2. A one-shot, low-complexity greedy algorithm is designed to provide an initial, feasible RB scheduling and SNR level assignment within each RB, guided by a priority policy based on the GF users' backoff times.
3. An iterative, coalition game-based algorithm is designed to further optimize user scheduling to RBs and SNR levels while minimizing transmission power consumption, with GF users acting independently as rational and self-interested players.
4. Numerical results based on modeling and simulation demonstrate that both scheduling algorithms yield a superior tradeoff between maximizing the number of admissible GF users and minimizing transmission energy consumption, compared to common user scheduling policies from the literature.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 presents the SGF NOMA and network secrecy models. Section 3 describes the process of quantizing discrete SNR levels for each RB and introduces the greedy and coalition game-based user scheduling algorithms. Section 4 presents the numerical evaluation, and Section 5 concludes the paper.

2 System Model

We consider the uplink of an SGF NOMA network, consisting of multiple GB users and multiple GF users, as illustrated in Fig. 1. Following the cognitive radio paradigm, GF users transparently access and share the dedicated resources

Fig. 1: Overview of the SGF NOMA network in the presence of an eavesdropper.

allocated to the GB users, enhancing spectrum utilization and reducing control signaling overhead. Let $\mathcal{N}_{GB} = \{1, \dots, N_{GB}\}$ and $\mathcal{N}_{GF} = \{1, \dots, N_{GF}\}$ denote the sets of GB and GF users, respectively. The network comprises a set of RBs, denoted by $\mathcal{M} = \{1, \dots, M\}$, where $M = N_{GB}$, such that each GB user is assigned a dedicated RB for uplink transmission. GF users opportunistically access and transmit over these RBs. Specifically, let $\mathcal{N}_{GF}^m = \{1, \dots, N_{GF}^m\}$ denote the set of GF users transmitting on RB $m \in \mathcal{M}$, assuming a one-to-one correspondence between the set of GB users and the set of RBs. The scheduling of GF users to the RBs should ensure that the QoS requirements of both GB and GF users in terms of uplink data rates are strictly satisfied. Let R_{GB} and R_{GF} [bps/Hz] denote the GB and GF users' minimum data rate requirements, respectively. Moreover, to further stress and challenge the system, an eavesdropper is considered in the network topology, attempting to intercept the GF users' uplink transmissions. Importantly, the secrecy of GB users is effectively resolved during the grant-request procedure, as their transmission power levels and rates can be appropriately configured to ensure secure communication.

2.1 Semi-Grant-Free NOMA Model

To facilitate the subsequent analysis, we focus on a specific RB $m \in \mathcal{M}$ assigned to a single GB user. In this RB, the corresponding GB user and the subset $\mathcal{N}_{GF}^m = \{1, \dots, N_{GF}^m\}$ of GF users, simultaneously transmit using the power-domain NOMA technique. Let h_{GB}^m and $h_{GF,j}^m$ denote the channel coefficients between the BS and the GB user and GF user $j \in \mathcal{N}_{GF}^m$, respectively, over RB $m \in \mathcal{M}$. To capture the effects of both large-scale path loss and small-scale fading, the channel coefficients are modeled as $|h_{GB}^m|^2 = |g_{GB}|^2 (d_{GB})^{-\alpha}$ and $|h_{GF,j}^m|^2 = |g_{GF}|^2 (d_{GF,j})^{-\alpha}$, respectively, where α is the path loss exponent, $g_{GB}, g_{GF} \sim \mathcal{CN}(0, 1)$ are the small-scale Rayleigh fading coefficients modeled as

circularly symmetric complex Gaussian random variables, and $d_{GB}, d_{GF,j}$ [m] are the Euclidean distances between the BS and GB user or GF user j , respectively.

The SNRs, which characterize the quality of the received signal at the BS in the absence of interference, are derived for the GB user and each GF user $j \in \mathcal{N}_{GF}^m$ on RB $m \in \mathcal{M}$ as:

$$\gamma_{GB}^m(P_{GB}^m) = \frac{P_{GB}^m |h_{GB}^m|^2}{\sigma^2}, \quad (1)$$

$$\gamma_{GF,j}^m(P_{GF,j}^m) = \frac{P_{GF,j}^m |h_{GF,j}^m|^2}{\sigma^2}, \quad (2)$$

where $P_{GB}^m, P_{GF,j}^m$ [W] are the uplink transmission powers, and σ^2 is the variance of Additive White Gaussian Noise (AWGN) at the receiver.

The BS employs the Successive Interference Cancellation (SIC) technique to decode the superimposed signal. The decoding process starts from the GB user's signal, which has the strongest received power, reducing latency. Therefore, the achievable data rate of the GB user on RB $m \in \mathcal{M}$ is given by:

$$R_{GB}^m = \log_2 \left(1 + \frac{\gamma_{GB}^m}{1 + \sum_{j' \in \mathcal{N}_{GF}^m} \gamma_{GF,j'}^m} \right), \quad [\text{bps/Hz}], \quad (3)$$

where the denominator includes the aggregate interference power resulting from all GF users simultaneously transmitting over the same RB.

Subsequently, the signals of the GF users are decoded in descending order of their SNR. Without loss of generality, it is assumed that the GF users on each RB $m \in \mathcal{M}$ are sorted in increasing order of their SNRs, i.e., $\gamma_{GF,1}^m \leq \dots \leq \gamma_{GF,j}^m \leq \dots \leq \gamma_{GF,N_{GF}^m}^m$. By following this decoding order, the achievable uplink data rate of GF user $j \in \mathcal{N}_{GF}^m$ on RB $m \in \mathcal{M}$ is given by:

$$R_{GF,j}^m = \log_2 \left(1 + \frac{\gamma_{GF,j}^m}{1 + \sum_{\substack{j' < j \\ j' \in \mathcal{N}_{GF}^m}} \gamma_{GF,j'}^m} \right), \quad [\text{bps/Hz}], \quad (4)$$

where the interference experienced by a GF user arises exclusively from GF users whose signals are decoded later in the SIC decoding order.

Consequently, predetermining the SNR levels of the GF users scheduled to a specific RB is sufficient to ensure that the data rate requirement of the corresponding GB user is satisfied, as will be demonstrated in Section 3.1.

2.2 Eavesdropper and Network Secrecy Model

An external active eavesdropper is considered within the SGF NOMA network, aiming to intercept the information transmitted by the GF users. Following common practices in the literature, the CSI of the eavesdropper is assumed to be available at the BS, obtained through advanced channel estimation techniques [5]. To ensure a robust and security-aware user scheduling design, a worst-case scenario is adopted, in which the eavesdropper is equipped with advanced

signal processing capabilities (e.g., parallel interference cancellation), enabling it to perfectly isolate and decode individual user signals, regardless of the interference structure [10]. While this assumption may exaggerate the eavesdropper's practical capabilities, it provides a meaningful security benchmark, ensuring that the proposed solution remains resilient under highly adverse conditions.

Let $h_{E,j}$ denote the channel coefficient between the eavesdropper and GF user $j \in \mathcal{N}_{GF}^m$, modeled as: $|h_{E,j}|^2 = |g_E|^2 (d_{E,j})^{-\alpha}$, where $g_E \sim \mathcal{CN}(0, 1)$ is the small-scale Rayleigh fading coefficient, and $d_{E,j}$ [m] is the Euclidean distance between the eavesdropper and GF user j . The SNR of the transmission from GF user $j \in \mathcal{N}_{GF}^m$ over RB $m \in \mathcal{M}$ at the eavesdropper is given by:

$$\gamma_{E,j}^m(P_{GF,j}^m) = \frac{P_{GF,j}^m |h_{E,j}^m|^2}{\sigma^2}. \quad (5)$$

Assuming that the eavesdropper can perfectly decode each GF user's signal without being affected by the interference from other users, the corresponding achieved eavesdropping rate for GF user j over RB m is:

$$R_{E,j}^m = \log_2(1 + \gamma_{E,j}^m), \quad [\text{bps/Hz}]. \quad (6)$$

The confidentiality of the transmission against potential interception is quantified through the secrecy rate of each GF user j over RB m , which is defined as the non-negative difference between the achievable data rate at the BS and the corresponding rate at the eavesdropper, and is formally expressed as:

$$R_{\text{sec},j}^m = [R_{GF,j}^m - R_{E,j}^m]^+, \quad [\text{bps/Hz}]. \quad (7)$$

To guarantee a secure transmission, the secrecy rate of each GF user must exceed a predefined secrecy rate threshold R_{sec} [bps/Hz], i.e., $R_{\text{sec},j}^m \geq R_{\text{sec}}$, $\forall m \in \mathcal{M}, j \in \mathcal{N}_{GF}^m$. Simultaneously, each GF user must meet its minimum data rate requirement R_{GF} to maintain an acceptable QoS level. These two requirements can be jointly enforced by imposing the following unified constraint on the achievable data rate of each GF user:

$$R_{GF,j}^m \geq \max(R_{GF}, R_{E,j}^m + R_{\text{sec}}). \quad (8)$$

Eq. (8) ensures that the GF user's data rate is sufficiently high to satisfy both the service quality and security requirements, thereby providing reliable and confidential uplink communication in the presence of an active eavesdropper.

3 Grant-Free Multi-RB Multi-User Scheduling

In this section, we introduce the proposed multi-RB multi-user scheduling framework within the considered SGF NOMA network, which, to the best of the authors' knowledge, is among the first in the literature grounded in low-complexity greedy and game-theoretic approaches.

The proposed framework employs predefined SNR levels as discrete admission thresholds for GF users within each RB. These levels, representing quantized target SNR values, are designed to satisfy the minimum service requirements of both GF and GB users. The SNR thresholds for each RB are broadcast by the BS during the initial preamble phase of the grant-free access procedure. Based on this broadcast, each GF user independently determines and configures its transmission power to an allowable SNR level, thereby becoming eligible for admission to the corresponding RB. Given the predefined SNR levels, two user scheduling algorithms are devised, operating either independently or in combination. The first is a computationally efficient greedy algorithm designed to provide prompt and effective scheduling decisions. The second approach leverages coalition game principles to enable distributed user grouping and resource sharing, aiming to minimize transmission power consumption through self-organized cooperation among GF users.

3.1 SNR Level Quantization

For each RB, the continuous range of possible SNR values for GF users is first quantized into a set of discrete SNR levels. This quantization facilitates coordinated admission and power control decisions on the GF users' behalf, ensuring compliance with both the SIC decoding order and the QoS requirements of GF and GB users. Let $\Gamma_m = \{\gamma_1^m, \dots, \gamma_l^m\}$, $l = 1, \dots, \infty$, and $\gamma_l < \gamma_{l'}$ for $l < l'$ denote the admissible SNR levels for GF users on RB $m \in \mathcal{M}$.

In the SGF NOMA model (Section 2.1), the GB user's signal is decoded first and is therefore subject to interference from the GF users. To ensure that the GB user's minimum data rate requirement on RB $m \in \mathcal{M}$ is met, the total interference sensed must be constrained below a certain threshold, which imposes an explicit limit on the cumulative interference of the predefined SNR levels as:

$$\begin{aligned} R_{GB}^m \geq R_{GB} &\implies \log_2 \left(1 + \frac{\gamma_{GB}^m}{1 + \sum_{j' \in \mathcal{N}_{GF}^m} \gamma_{j'}^m} \right) \geq R_{GB} \\ &\implies \sum_{j' \in \mathcal{N}_{GF}^m} \gamma_{j'}^m \leq \frac{\gamma_{GB}^m}{2^{R_{GB}} - 1} - 1 = \tau^m, \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

where τ^m defines the maximum allowable cumulative interference power that all admitted GF users on RB $m \in \mathcal{M}$ can introduce, preserving the GB user's QoS.

For the GF users, the assignment of SNR levels follows a hierarchical structure aligned with the SIC decoding order. Each GF user must achieve an SNR sufficient to satisfy its minimum data rate requirement R_{GF} , while accounting for the interference from all users decoded later in the decoding order. The GF user with the highest SNR is decoded first and thus experiences the highest level of interference from all other GF users, while the GF user with the lowest SNR is decoded last, benefiting from complete interference cancellation as no residual interference remains. To maximize GF user admission in an RB, the number of distinct SNR levels that support successful transmission must be maximized.

Accordingly, the SNR level of the GF user with the lowest received signal power is set to the minimum value required to marginally meet its QoS constraint, i.e., $R_{GF,1}^m = \log_2(1 + \gamma_1^m) = R_{GF}$, which directly yields the minimum received SNR level: $\gamma_1^m = 2^{R_{GF}} - 1$.

For GF users decoded earlier in the SIC decoding order, the received SNR must be sufficiently high to overcome both thermal noise and the interference introduced by all subsequently decoded users. Thus, GF user $j \in \mathcal{N}_{GF}^m$ on RB $m \in \mathcal{M}$ must satisfy the following condition to marginally achieve its minimum data rate requirement:

$$R_{GF,j}^m = \log_2 \left(1 + \frac{\gamma_j^m}{1 + \sum_{\substack{j' < j \\ j' \in \mathcal{N}_{GF}^m}} \gamma_{j'}^m} \right) = R_{GF}, \quad (10)$$

which implies the following recursive SNR relation:

$$\gamma_j^m = \begin{cases} 2^{R_{GF}} - 1, & \text{for } j = 1, \\ (2^{R_{GF}} - 1) \left(1 + \sum_{\substack{j' < j \\ j' \in \mathcal{N}_{GF}^m}} \gamma_{j'}^m \right), & \text{for } j > 1. \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

This recursive formulation generates a monotonically increasing sequence of SNR levels within each RB m , consistent with the SIC decoding order and the cumulative nature of the interference experienced by earlier-decoded GF users. At this point, it should be noted that the calculation of the SNR levels is independent of the secrecy constraint R_{sec} in Eq. (8), the satisfaction of which requires knowledge of each user's eavesdropping channel conditions that cannot be generalized or accurately predicted before users' transmissions.

Overall, the aggregated interference introduced by all admitted GF users on each RB m must strictly adhere to the upper bound τ^m , which is determined by the QoS requirement of the GB user. Consequently, the maximum number of GF users that can be concurrently admitted to RB m , denoted by N_{max}^m , and therefore the maximum number of SNR levels, is dynamically determined by Eq. (9), the recursive relation (Eq. (11)) and the specific system parameters. Once N_{max}^m for each RB $m \in \mathcal{M}$ is determined, the corresponding set of admissible SNR levels is updated accordingly as $\Gamma_m = \{\gamma_1^m, \dots, \gamma_{N_{max}^m}^m\}$ based on Eq. (11). If the lowest SNR level γ_1^m exceeds the allowable interference threshold τ^m on RB m , then no GF user is scheduled on this RB, and the GB user is exclusively served.

3.2 Greedy Scheduling Algorithm

A low-complexity contention-based algorithm is first designed to orchestrate GF user scheduling across the available RBs, aiming to maximize the number of admitted GF users while ensuring reliable communication and system constraint satisfaction. The operation of the greedy algorithm is presented subsequently.

At the beginning of each scheduling interval, the BS constructs an ordered list of all available SNR levels across all RBs \mathcal{M} in the system. Let $\Gamma = \bigcup_{m \in \mathcal{M}} \Gamma_m = \{\gamma_1, \dots, \gamma_l, \dots, \gamma_{N_{max}}\}$ denote the ordered list of GF-eligible SNR levels across all RBs. The objective is to allocate these SNR levels to GF users in a manner that prioritizes those with a higher probability of successfully attaining the assigned SNR while adhering to their individual constraints.

To initiate the contention phase, the BS broadcasts a contention window duration t_{max} , within which all GF users are expected to transmit a preamble signal. Although a preamble-based RACH procedure is employed for initial alignment, subsequent data transmissions occur without requiring individual scheduling grants, preserving the grant-free nature of the scheme [3]. This approach enables efficient user identification and resource allocation while avoiding the signaling overhead of conventional grant-based access. Specifically, each GF user $j \in \mathcal{N}_{GF}$ selects a backoff time $t_{GF,j} \in (0, t_{max}]$ in seconds, computed using a monotonically decreasing function $f(\cdot)$ of its effective SNR, which accounts for both the direct link to the BS and the eavesdropper link. GF users with better channel conditions select shorter backoff times and thus transmit their preambles earlier. The backoff time of GF user $j \in \mathcal{N}_{GF}$ is defined as follows:

$$t_{GF,j} = \min \left\{ f \left(\log_2 \left(\frac{(\gamma_{GF,j}^m (P_{GF,j}^{max}))^2}{(\gamma_{E,j}^m (P_{GF,j}^{max}))^2} \right) \right), t_{max} \right\}, \quad [\text{sec}], \quad (12)$$

where $f(\cdot)$ a strictly decreasing function and $P_{GF,j}^{max}$ [W] the maximum transmission power of GF user $j \in \mathcal{N}_{GF}$.

At the end of the contention window, the BS identifies the GF users based on the order of their preamble arrivals. These users are sequentially assigned to the available SNR levels across all RBs, starting from the highest, in reverse order of their preamble transmission times, i.e., earlier transmitters are assigned higher SNR levels. Each admitted user is allocated to a specific RB and associated with the corresponding SNR level. The maximum number of GF users that can be admitted is determined by the total number of available SNR levels across all RBs, i.e., $N_{max} = \sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}} N_{max}^m$. Only the first N_{max} GF users, according to the preamble arrival order, are considered for admission, ensuring efficient utilization of the available resources.

The BS broadcasts the indices $j \in \{0, N_{max}\}$ of the GF users, preserving the order of preamble reception at the BS. Based on this order, each GF user autonomously determines its assigned SNR level $l_j = \Gamma[N_{max} - j + 1]$, effectively mapping earlier preamble transmissions to higher SNR levels. By prioritizing the assignment of higher SNR levels to users with better channels, the system increases the likelihood that users can satisfy their power constraints, thereby maximizing the number of GF users admitted into the system. Each GF user computes the transmission power required to achieve the designated SNR level, verifying that it does not exceed its maximum transmit power budget $P_{GF,j}^{max}$. If the power constraint is satisfied, the user then assesses whether the resulting transmission meets its secrecy rate requirement. If either the power constraint

Algorithm 1 Greedy Scheduling Algorithm

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- 1: **Input:** $\mathcal{N}_{GF}, \mathcal{M}, P_{GF,j}^{max}, \forall j \in \mathcal{N}_{GF}, N_{max}$
 - 2: **Output:** Admitted GF users with assigned RBs and SNR levels.
 - 3: BS constructs an ordered list $\Gamma = \{\gamma_1, \dots, \gamma_l, \dots, \gamma_{N_{max}}\}$ of all SNR levels across RBs \mathcal{M} in ascending order.
 - 4: BS broadcasts Γ and a contention window t_{max} .
 - 5: **for all** GF users $j \in \mathcal{N}_{GF}$ **do**
 - 6: Compute backoff time $t_{GF,j} = \min \left\{ f \left(\log_2 \left(\frac{(\gamma_{GF,j}^m (P_{GF,j}^{max}))^2}{(\gamma_{E,j}^m (P_{GF,j}^{max}))^2} \right) \right), t_{max} \right\}$.
 - 7: **end for**
 - 8: Each GF user collects the preambles of all other users and sorts them by ascending $t_{GF,j}$ order.
 - 9: Each GF user determines whether it belongs to the first N_{max} GF users.
 - 10: **for** $j = 1$ to N_{max} **do**
 - 11: User j selects the SNR level $l_j = \Gamma[N_{max} - j + 1]$ within RB m .
 - 12: User j determines its transmission power $P_{GF,j}$ to achieve SNR level l_j .
 - 13: **if** $P_{GF,j} > P_{GF,j}^{max}$ **or** secrecy constraint (8) violated **then**
 - 14: User j declines the assignment and is excluded.
 - 15: **else**
 - 16: User j is admitted to RB m with SNR level l_j .
 - 17: **end if**
 - 18: **end for**
-

or the secrecy rate requirement is violated, the user rejects the assignment and is excluded from scheduling. Otherwise, the user is admitted to the RB and allocated the corresponding SNR level. This rigorous verification process ensures that only users capable of satisfying both their power and secrecy constraints are scheduled. The proposed greedy scheduling algorithm is summarized in Algorithm 1.

3.3 Coalition Game-Based Scheduling

The Greedy algorithm presented in Section 3.2 offers a one-shot, low-complexity solution for generating an initial feasible user scheduling. To further optimize both user scheduling and power consumption, a distributed and iterative approach based on coalition games is also introduced. Coalition games constitute a class of cooperative games that enable rational players to dynamically reorganize their associations in pursuit of improved system collective utility.

In the coalition game, the GF users are modeled as rational players seeking to maximize their utility, which is inversely related to their transmission power consumption, while satisfying system QoS requirements. Each coalition corresponds to a unique RB, and the utility function for each GF user $j \in \mathcal{N}_{GF}$ assigned to coalition $m \in \mathcal{M}$ with SNR level $\gamma_j^m \in \Gamma_m$ and transmission power

$P_{GF,j}^m$ is expressed as:

$$u_j(m, \gamma_j^m, P_{GF,j}^m) = \frac{P_{GF,j}^{max} - P_{GF,j}^m}{P_{GF,j}^{max}}. \quad (13)$$

The goal of the game is to optimize user scheduling into coalitions such that the coalition-wide utility, defined as the sum of individual user utilities within each coalition, is maximized. Formally, the coalition game is defined as follows.

Definition 1. (Coalition Game) *The coalition game is represented by $(\mathcal{N}_{GF}, \mathcal{M}, u)$, defined as follows:*

- \mathcal{N}_{GF} is the set of GF users transmitting in the SGF system,
- \mathbb{M} is the set of available coalitions, each defined by an RB. Each GF user selects only one RB.
- $\mathcal{L}^m = \{l_1^m, \dots, l_i^m, \dots, l_{N_{max}^m}^m\}$ is the set of SNR levels assignment for coalition m , i.e., $l_i^m = j$ if GF user $j \in \mathcal{N}_{GF}$ is assigned to the i -th SNR level, $i \in \{1, \dots, N_{max}^m\}$, of coalition $m \in \mathcal{M}$.
- $u(m, \mathcal{L}^m) = \sum_{\forall j \in \mathcal{N}_{GF}^m} u_j(m, \gamma_j, P_{GF,j}^m)$ denotes the total utility of coalition m .

Each GF user initially belongs to exactly one coalition or remains unassigned. The coalition game enables users to dynamically join or switch coalitions if such moves lead to an increase in the total system utility, while satisfying the feasibility conditions, such as the maximum power budget and secrecy constraints. These reallocation decisions are governed by a set of formally defined switching rules, which specify the necessary and sufficient conditions under which a user may join or exchange coalition memberships, subject to both feasibility and utility improvement criteria.

Definition 2. (Switch Rules) *The following rules must be followed in the coalition game:*

Rule 1 (Join Coalition): *For a GF user $j \in \mathcal{N}_{GF}$ who is not in any coalition, j will join a coalition m that has at least one available SNR level γ_i^m , $i \in \{1, \dots, N_{max}^m\}$, i.e., $l_i^m = \emptyset$, if:*

1. $\exists P_{GF,j}^m \in (0, P_{GF,j}^{max}]$, such that user j achieves SNR level γ_j^m ,
2. Secrecy constraint (Eq. (8)) is satisfied when transmitting with $P_{GF,j}^m$,
3. $m = \operatorname{argmax}_{m^* \in \mathbb{M}} \{u(m^* \cup \{j\}, \mathcal{L}^{m^*} \cup \{l_i^m = j\}) - u(m^*, \mathcal{L}^{m^*}) | u(m^* \cup \{j\}, \mathcal{L}^{m^*} \cup \{l_i^m = j\}) - u(m^*, \mathcal{L}^{m^*}) > 0\}$.

The new set of coalitions is $\mathbb{M} = \{\mathbb{M} \setminus \{m\}\} \cup \{m \cup \{j\}\}$ and the SNR level assignment for coalition m is updated as: $\mathcal{L}^m = \mathcal{L}^m \cup \{l_i^m = j\}$.

Rule 2 (Switch Coalition): *For $j \in \mathcal{N}_{GF}^m$ and coalition m' , j will leave the original coalition $m \neq m'$ and the assigned SNR level γ_i^m , $i \in \{1, \dots, N_{max}^m\}$, and join another coalition m' that has at least one available SNR level $\gamma_{i'}^{m'}$, $i' \in \{1, \dots, N_{max}^{m'}\}$, $l_{i'}^{m'} = \emptyset$, if:*

1. $\exists P_{GF,j}^{m'} \in (0, P_{GF,j}^{max}]$, such that user j achieves SNR level $\gamma_{j'}^{m'}$,

2. Secrecy constraint (Eq. (8)) is satisfied when transmitting with $P_{GF,j}^{m'}$,
3. $u(m \setminus \{j\}, \mathcal{L}^m \cup \{l_i^m = \emptyset\}) + u(m' \cup \{j\}, \mathcal{L}^{m'} \cup \{l_{i'}^{m'} = j\}) > u(m, \mathcal{L}^m) + u(m', \mathcal{L}^{m'})$.

The new set of coalitions is $\mathbb{M} = \{\{\mathbb{M} \setminus \{m, m'\}\} \cup \{m \setminus \{j\}\} \cup \{m' \cup \{j\}\}\}$ and the SNR level assignments for coalition m are updated as: $\mathcal{L}^m = \mathcal{L}^m \cup \{l_i^m = \emptyset\}$ and $\mathcal{L}^{m'} = \mathcal{L}^{m'} \cup \{l_{i'}^{m'} = j\}$, respectively.

Rule 3 (Swap Coalitions): For $j \in \mathcal{N}_{GF}^m$ and $j' \in \mathcal{N}_{GF}^{m'}$, $j' \neq j$, j and j' swap coalitions and corresponding SNR levels γ_i^m , $i \in \{1, \dots, N_{max}^m\}$, and $\gamma_{i'}^{m'}$, $i' \in \{1, \dots, N_{max}^{m'}\}$, respectively, if:

1. $\exists P_{GF,j}^{m'} \in (0, P_{GF,j}^{max}]$, such that user j achieves SNR level $\gamma_{i'}^{m'}$ and $\exists P_{GF,j'}^m \in (0, P_{GF,j'}^{max}]$, such that user j' achieves SNR level γ_i^m ,
2. Secrecy constraint (Eq. (8)) is satisfied for both users j and j' when transmitting with $P_{GF,j}^{m'}$ and $P_{GF,j'}^m$, respectively,
3. $u((m \setminus \{j\}) \cup \{j'\}, \mathcal{L}^m \cup \{l_i^m = j'\}) + u((m' \setminus \{j'\}) \cup \{j\}, \mathcal{L}^{m'} \cup \{l_{i'}^{m'} = j\}) > u(m, \mathcal{L}^m) + u(m', \mathcal{L}^{m'})$.

Algorithm 2 Coalition Game Algorithm

- 1: **Input:** $\mathbb{M}_{initial}$ based on Greedy Algorithm scheduling output, P_{sel} , τ_{max} .
 - 2: **Output:** Optimal Coalition Partition \mathbb{M}^* .
 - 3: **repeat**
 - 4: With probability P_{sel} , randomly select an unscheduled GF user $j \in \mathcal{N}_{GF}$, its coalition $m \in \mathcal{M}$, and assigned SNR level $l_i^m, i \in \{1, \dots, N_{max}^m\}$.
 - 5: **if** j does not belong to any coalition and $\exists m$ that satisfies **Rule 1** **then**
 - 6: Update $\mathbb{M} = \{\mathbb{M} \setminus \{m\}\} \cup \{m \cup \{j\}\}$ and $\mathcal{L}^m = \mathcal{L}^m \cup \{l_i^m = j\}$.
 - 7: **else**
 - 8: Another coalition $m', m' \neq m$ is randomly selected.
 - 9: **if** $\exists l_{i'}^{m'} \in \mathcal{L}^{m'}, l_{i'}^{m'} = \emptyset$ **then**
 - 10: **if** conditions of **Rule 2** are satisfied **then**
 - 11: Update $\mathbb{M} = \{\mathbb{M} \setminus \{m, m'\}\} \cup \{m \setminus \{j\}\} \cup \{m' \cup \{j\}\}$,
 $\mathcal{L}^m = \mathcal{L}^m \cup \{l_i^m = \emptyset\}$ and $\mathcal{L}^{m'} = \mathcal{L}^{m'} \cup \{l_{i'}^{m'} = j\}$.
 - 12: **end if**
 - 13: **else**
 - 14: Randomly select a user $j' \in \mathcal{N}_{GF}^{m'}$ of coalition m' with its assigned SNR level $l_{i'}^{m'}, i' \in \{1, \dots, N_{max}^{m'}\}$.
 - 15: **if** conditions of **Rule 3** are satisfied **then**
 - 16: Update $\mathbb{M} = \{\mathbb{M} \setminus \{m, m'\}\} \cup \{(m \setminus \{j\}) \cup \{j'\}\} \cup \{(m' \setminus \{j'\}) \cup \{j\}\}$,
 $\mathcal{L}^m = \mathcal{L}^m \cup \{l_i^m = j'\}$ and $\mathcal{L}^{m'} = \mathcal{L}^{m'} \cup \{l_{i'}^{m'} = j\}$.
 - 17: **end if**
 - 18: **end if**
 - 19: **end if**
 - 20: **until** No further user scheduling updates for τ_{max} consecutive iterations.
-

The new set of coalitions is $\mathbb{M} = \{\{\mathbb{M} \setminus \{m, m'\}\} \cup \{(m \setminus \{j\}) \cup \{j'\}\} \cup \{(m' \setminus \{j'\}) \cup \{j\}\}\}$ and the SNR level assignments for coalition m and m' are updated as: $\mathcal{L}^m = \mathcal{L}^m \cup \{l_i^m = j'\}$ and $\mathcal{L}^{m'} = \mathcal{L}^{m'} \cup \{l_{i'}^{m'} = j\}$, respectively.

At each game iteration, a GF user is selected according to a probabilistic scheme that favors unassigned users. Specifically, the probability of selecting an unscheduled user is P_{sel} . This biased selection mechanism facilitates the expedited user scheduling of the currently lacking coalition assignment. The iterative procedure proceeds until convergence is achieved, which is formally defined as the condition under which no modifications in user assignments occur over a predetermined number of consecutive iterations τ_{max} . This state signifies that the coalition structure has reached stability and that no further enhancements in the overall coalition utility are attainable. The complete process of the Coalition Game is detailed in Algorithm 2.

4 Evaluation & Results

In this section, we evaluate the performance of the proposed greedy and coalition game-based user scheduling mechanisms through modeling and simulation. The objective is to assess their efficiency in terms of the number of successfully admitted GF users and the incurred power consumption under interference and security constraints. In our experiments, we consider a square area of 1000×1000 m², with a BS located at the center of the area, at coordinates (500, 500), while an eavesdropper is positioned at (100, 100). A total of $N_{GB} = 5$ GB users are randomly deployed within the area. The available radio spectrum is divided into $M = 5$ orthogonal RBs, with each GB user exclusively assigned to one RB. Following the interference and secrecy scheduling constraints derived in Section 3.1 (Eq. (9) and Eq. (11)), the maximum allowable number of GF users for each RB, N_{max}^m , is computed to guarantee the QoS of the GB users.

Subsequently, a total of $N_{GF} = N_{max}$ GF users are uniformly distributed across the area, targeting access to one of the RBs for their transmissions. Unless otherwise specified, the target transmission rates for GB and GF users are set as $R_{GB} = 1.2$ bps/Hz and $R_{GF} = 1$ bps/Hz, respectively, with a required secrecy rate of $R_{sec} = 0.2$ bps/Hz. The rest of the communication-related parameters are defined as: $\alpha = 3.7$, $P_{GF,j}^{max} = 1$ W, $\forall j \in \mathcal{N}_{GF}$ and $P_{GB}^m = 1$ W, $\forall m \in \mathcal{M}$. Regarding the coalition game-based algorithm, it is assumed that: $P_{sel} = 75\%$ and $\tau_{max} = 50$ iterations. Moreover, two user admission policies are considered: (i) the **Max** policy, where each RB $m \in \mathcal{M}$ admits up to N_{max}^m GF users, and (ii) the **Balanced** policy, where only $\frac{N_{max}^m}{2}$ are admitted per RB $m \in \mathcal{M}$. Unless explicitly stated otherwise, the Max admission policy is applied, as it represents a more challenging scenario. In this case, the higher number of admitted GF users increases the risk of interference, making efficient user scheduling more complex and thus providing a stricter evaluation environment for the proposed algorithms. In contrast, the Balanced policy reduces contention and interference, thereby enabling more efficient power consumption.

Fig. 2: Impact of QoS requirements and eavesdropper presence on GF user admission.

Fig. 3: Number of unscheduled GF users under the proposed scheduling mechanisms and sorting criteria.

First, we evaluate the impact of varying QoS requirements on the system's GF user admission. Specifically, Fig. 2 illustrates the number of GF users that are admitted to the system through the coalition game-based scheduling as a function of the data rate requirements imposed on both GF and GB users. The analysis is conducted for scenarios with and without the presence of an eavesdropper, thereby capturing the influence of secrecy constraints on the system's capacity. A monotonic decrease in the number of admitted users is observed as the QoS requirements for GF users become more stringent. This reduction stems from the fact that achieving higher data rates necessitates an increase in SNR for each GF user, which directly impacts the interference budget at each RB. Specifically, as the SNR requirements increase, the maximum tolerable interference τ^m at each RB is reached with fewer GF users, thereby reducing the number of admissible users that can be simultaneously scheduled.

A similar trend is observed with respect to the data rate requirements of the GB users. As the QoS requirements for GB users increase, the system imposes more stringent interference constraints to ensure their performance targets are met. Consequently, the admission of additional GF users becomes increasingly restricted. Moreover, the presence of an eavesdropper further exacerbates this limitation in both cases. The additional secrecy constraints introduced by the requirement to satisfy a target secrecy rate effectively reduce the feasible set of GF users that can be admitted without compromising the system's security. Notably, the eavesdropper's impact on GF user admission is more pronounced when QoS requirements for both types are relaxed. As these requirements become stricter, QoS constraints dominate the system, rendering the admission performance with or without the eavesdropper comparable.

Building upon this analysis, we next focus on evaluating the efficiency of the proposed greedy and coalition game-based scheduling mechanisms under different sorting criteria applied to the backoff time assignment process (Eq. (12)). The sorting criterion plays a crucial role in determining the order in which GF

users contend for RB access, thus directly influencing the likelihood of successful scheduling for each user. To this end, we benchmark the proposed criterion against widely adopted alternatives from the literature: (i) **MUS Criterion** [5]: Users are prioritized exclusively based on their SNR at the BS, with backoff time $t_{GF,j} = \min \{f(\log_2(1 + \gamma_{GF,j}^m(P_{GF,j}^{max}))), t_{max}\}, \forall j \in \mathcal{N}_{GF}$, (ii) **OUS Criterion** [5]: Both direct links to the BS and eavesdropper links are considered via the corresponding SNRs, i.e., $t_{GF,j} = \min \left\{ f \left(\log_2 \left(\frac{1 + \gamma_{GF,j}^m(P_{GF,j}^{max})}{1 + \gamma_{E,j}^m(P_{GF,j}^{max})} \right) \right), t_{max} \right\}$, (iii) **PR Criterion**: Users are sorted based on the product of legitimate and eavesdropper SNRs, i.e., $t_{GF,j} = \min \{f(\gamma_{GF,j}^m(P_{GF,j}^{max}) \cdot \gamma_{E,j}^m(P_{GF,j}^{max})), t_{max}\}$, and, (iv) **Random Criterion**: No sorting is applied, backoff times are uniformly drawn as $t_{GF,j} \sim \mathcal{U}(0, t_{max})$. In all cases, the selected metric governs the backoff time $t_{GF,j}$ of each GF user j , thereby implicitly controlling the admission probability.

Fig. 3 illustrates the number of GF users that remain unscheduled following the application of the greedy and coalition game-based scheduling mechanisms under the proposed and benchmark sorting criteria. As observed, the proposed criterion consistently achieves the lowest number of unscheduled users across all scenarios, with approximately only one GF user remaining unassigned in the majority of the cases. By explicitly considering the SNR at the BS while inversely weighting the influence of the SNR at the eavesdropper, the proposed approach effectively prioritizes users that maximize security without compromising QoS constraints. Moreover, the results highlight the benefits of employing the coalition game following the greedy scheduling phase. In all examined scenarios, the application of the coalition formation algorithm further reduces the number of unscheduled users, demonstrating its effectiveness in exploiting cooperative dynamics among GF users to improve overall resource utilization. Based on this analysis, in all subsequent performance evaluations presented in this section, the proposed sorting criterion is adopted as the default mechanism for backoff time assignment.

Next, a comparative performance evaluation of the proposed scheduling mechanisms against approaches inspired by the existing literature is performed. To enable a fair comparison and assess the efficiency of our proposed multi-RB multi-user framework, we introduce two variations that extend the benchmark sorting criteria to the multi-RB setting:

1. **Multi-Resource Block (mRB) MUS, OUS, Random Scheduling**: In this approach, GF users are randomly assigned to one of the available RBs, respecting the maximum admission capacity $N_{max}^m, \forall m \in \mathcal{M}$. Subsequently, within each RB, the respective benchmark sorting criterion (i.e., MUS, OUS, Random) is applied to determine the scheduling order of GF users to SNR levels, following the contention-based process as in the proposed mechanisms. Under this approach, if a user is not admitted to the initially allocated RB, it remains unscheduled and excluded from transmission.
2. **Repetitive Multi-Resource Block (Rep. mRB) MUS, OUS, Random Scheduling**: This variation builds upon the previous mRB scenarios by allowing unscheduled GF users to reattempt RB access in subsequent

Fig. 4: Number of unscheduled GF users under comparative scheduling mechanisms and different admission policies. Fig. 5: Mean transmission power of scheduled GF users for different scheduling approaches and admission policies.

iterations. Specifically, in each time slot, unscheduled users are reallocated to a new RB according to the same random assignment procedure, followed by the application of the benchmark sorting criterion for scheduling. This iterative process continues until a maximum number of τ_{max} iterations is reached.

Fig. 4 and Fig. 5 present the number of unscheduled GF users and the average transmission power of scheduled GF users, respectively, under the proposed mechanisms and the comparative scenarios, considering both the "Balanced" and "Max" admission policies. Focusing at the number of unscheduled users, it is evident that the proposed approach, which is specifically tailored to efficiently address the multi-RB, multi-user scheduling problem, consistently outperforms all scenarios. In particular, this behavior highlights the effectiveness of the proposed frameworks in maximizing user admission under both policies.

Regarding power consumption, it is observed that the proposed greedy algorithm introduces an increase in the average transmission power compared to the other approaches. This outcome is expected, as the greedy algorithm prioritizes maximizing the number of successfully admitted GF users within each RB, potentially requiring higher transmission powers to meet the QoS and secrecy constraints. For instance, when compared to the most power-efficient benchmark scenario, Rep. mRB MUS scheme, the proposed greedy algorithm results in an approximately 14.41% increase in average transmission power. However, this increase is accompanied by a significant reduction of nearly 51.49% in the number of unscheduled GF users, clearly highlighting the tradeoff between user admission and power efficiency. In contrast, the coalition game-based mechanism, which incorporates the transmission power of GF users as part of its utility function, achieves the most energy-efficient outcome among all considered methods. This highlights the ability of the coalition formation process to promote more power-

Fig. 6: Scalability analysis of the number of scheduled users under a varying number of RBs.

conscious scheduling decisions without compromising the number of scheduled users.

Comparing the simple mRB and repetitive mRB variations, it is observed that the repetitive approach consistently achieves marginal improvements in both metrics, as the iterative reallocation process provides additional opportunities for unscheduled users to gain RB access. Furthermore, the application of the Balanced admission policy yields superior results across all methods, as the stricter admission control reduces the risk of excessive interference within the RBs, ultimately enhancing both user scheduling and power efficiency.

Finally, to evaluate the robustness and practical applicability of the proposed framework, we conduct a scalability analysis. Specifically, we examine how the system performance evolves as the number of GF users and available RBs increases. Fig. 6 depicts the total number of GF users present in the system, along with the number of scheduled GF users, as a function of the total RBs for both proposed algorithms under the different admission policies. Moreover, Table 1 presents the corresponding percentage of scheduled GF users for the two algorithms and all considered admission policies. To ensure fairness across scenarios, the number of GF users in the system is determined based on the permitted SNR levels defined by each admission policy. This approach guarantees that the system load scales consistently with the available resources and that performance comparisons remain meaningful across different configurations.

As anticipated, increasing the number of RBs leads to a proportional increase in both the numbers of GF users in the system and the successfully scheduled users. Focusing on the admission percentages, it is observed that, regardless of the total RBs, the proposed algorithms consistently achieve a high admission rate (approximately 95%). The coalition game-based algorithm further improves the performance in all scenarios by promoting cooperative dynamics. Notably, under the Balanced admission policy, the system consistently schedules all GF users. In contrast, in the Max admission policy, where a more competitive environment is imposed, a small percentage of GF users remain unscheduled.

Table 1: Percentage of scheduled GF Users for increasing number of RB and different admission policies.

Number of RBs	Max Policy		Balanced Policy	
	Greedy (%)	Coalition (%)	Greedy (%)	Coalition (%)
3	95.38	95.75	100	100
4	93.83	94.18	100	100
5	93.46	94.08	100	100
6	94.89	95.42	100	100
7	95.40	95.88	100	100
8	95.04	95.22	100	100

5 Conclusion

In this paper, we introduced a novel framework for secure and power-efficient scheduling for multi-user SGF wireless systems operating over multiple RBs. Each RB serves a GB user whose transmission must meet strict QoS requirements and be protected from harmful interference, while GF users opportunistically access the same RB under carefully controlled interference constraints. A user sorting criterion was introduced that jointly considers the legitimate user's and the eavesdropper's impact to enhance admission decisions under QoS and physical layer security constraints. The proposed mechanism combines a greedy user assignment phase with a coalition game-based refinement, enabling power-efficient resource utilization by leveraging cooperative dynamics among GF users across multiple RBs. Numerical results demonstrated the superiority of the proposed approach over state-of-the-art benchmark schemes in minimizing unscheduled users, maintaining secrecy rates, and optimizing transmission power under different admission policies. Furthermore, the analysis revealed the trade-offs between user admission and power consumption, as well as the varying impact of eavesdropping depending on the strictness of the QoS requirements.

Part of our future work will focus on exploring Reinforcement Learning (RL) techniques to further enhance the scheduling resource allocation process presented in this paper. By leveraging RL's ability to explore large state-action spaces in stochastic environments, we aim to develop adaptive solutions that more effectively navigate the complex tradeoffs among user admission, QoS requirements, and security constraints in real time.

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